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Monitoring Badlands Features through TLS and UAV Technology

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Abstract—High-resolution Point Clouds (PC), obtained from Terrestrial Laser Scanner and Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)-based surveys (both LiDAR and RGB), enables the precise detection of topographical changes, essential for advanced geomorphological analysis. This study evaluates the performance of both methods in a badlands area near Aliano (Basilicata region, southern Italy), characterized by distinctive dome-shaped landforms known as *biancane*. The complex morphology investigated presents challenges for these techniques, requiring exceptionally detailed modeling to capture subtle topographical variations with accuracy. These factors introduce potential sources of error that must be addressed to ensure reliable analysis. Furthermore, another source of errors depends on the type of landscape monitored. In this study we compare PCs derived from different monitoring techniques to define the best practices in combining remote sensing surveys, and to evaluate their strengths, limitations, and potential synergies in monitoring highly complex geomorphological features. By integrating insights from both approaches, we aim to establish best practices for combined remote sensing techniques in the study of badlands and other complex terrains. The preliminary results provide a framework for the selection and optimization of monitoring methodologies based on landscape complexity and project objectives, contributing to the broader application of remote sensing in geomorphology.

I. INTRODUCTION

High-resolution Point Cloud (PC) reconstructions from Terrestrial Laser Scanner (TLS) and Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)-based surveys have significantly improved advancements in geomorphological analyses. Thanks to their very high resolution, PCs enable the detection of topographical changes in ranges of few cm/y to some mm/y [1,2]. However, both technologies present distinct advantages and limitations. UAV and

TLS provide complementary benefits in terms of geomorphological analysis, offering high-resolution data for mapping, and monitoring landscape features. UAVs are cost-effective and versatile, making them ideal for surveying remote areas, while TLS provides detailed 3D measurements of surface features [3,4].

Therefore, the integration of these two technologies has the potential to improve spatial coverage, and data accuracy, by combining the broad accessibility of UAV, with the precision of laser scanning. Nonetheless, challenges including specialized expertise, data processing and accuracy, and potential limitations in distance range and line of sight in variable environmental conditions, highlight the importance of addressing these issues for their effective integration into geomorphological research.

In this context, we assessed the combined PC reconstructions derived from UAV-based Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) and RGB sensors, comparing them with those generated from TLS. Key evaluation parameters included point density, scene coverage, surface roughness, and accuracy, giving particular attention to errors introduced by the area's complex morphology [5]. TLS-derived PCs offer a superior resolution for those areas that are in the line of sight, but the lack of complete coverage on complex slopes represents a drawback. On the contrary, UAV-based PCs (both RGB and LiDAR) provide broader scene coverage, suffering, however, from lower point density and a limited penetration under vegetation [6,7].

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of PCs derived from the above-described methodologies in characterizing complex terrain morphology of *biancane* landforms in Basilicata to state the best strategy for integration. PCs were further validated against in-situ data allowing a more effective analysis. The results facilitated the assessment of geomorphological changes, including

the rates of erosion and deposition, while offering insights into the underlying factors driving these processes. This combined approach provides a robust framework to understand the *biancane* landforms dynamics.

The study area, ~55000m² wide, is located near Aliano, (Matera) in Basilicata (southern Italy), close the Sauro-Agri river confluence, at an altitude of about 200 m above sea level (Fig. 1). The topography is characterised by a gently NE-dipping monocline with rocks exposed to the S and SW steeper slopes. The area represents the NE portion of the Plio-Pleistocene Sant’Arcangelo basin [8–10], where grey-blue, shallow-marine marly clays, and limited beds of yellowish silty-sandy clays, are the main geological formations [11]. *Biancane*, micropediments, and gullies are the main landforms in the area [2,12,13].

Figure 1. a) Location of the studied area in southern Italy. Base map: Google Satellite; b) view of dome shaped features (*biancane*) in the area; c) extend of UAV-based and TLS surveys.

II. METHODS

All datasets were collected at the same time, on May 10, 2024. The acquisitions were performed with a DJI Mavic 3M, equipped with a 20 MP RGB camera and with a DJI Matrice 350 with a LiDAR sensor Zenmuse L1. Both sensors were used to conduct flight missions at angles of 90° (ortho collection) and 45° (oblique collection). The flight mission’s settings are summarized in Table I.

DJI Terra [14] was used for both RGB and LiDAR data processing: image post-processing followed the principles of Structure-from-Motion techniques [15].

TABLE I. FLIGHT MISSION SETTINGS

	DJI Mavic 3M (RGB)	DJI Matrice 350 RTK (LiDAR)
Flight height (m)	50	50
Paths direction	E-W	E-W
Ortho GSD (cm/pix)	1.34	1.36
Oblique GSD (cm/pix)	1.9	1.93
Side Overlap (%)	70	20
Forward Overlap (%)	80	

TLS data were collected with a FARO Laser Scanner Focus 3D in 7 positions in and around the study site. PCs registration, georeferencing, and dataset comparison were done using the Cloud Compare free software (www.cloudcompare.org, version 2.13.2 Kharkiv, 2024). The total root mean square (RMS) error for registration processing is 2.23 cm and 3.01 cm for georeferencing. Point cloud roughness was computed to monitor how the points are scattered on the model. We applied Cloud Compare roughness tool, that is the distance between each point, and the best fitting plane computed on its nearest neighbors (<https://www.cloudcompare.org/doc/wiki/index.php/Roughness>). In addition, we used the M3C2 plugin [16] to detect changes among different datasets.

III. RESULTS

Multi-platform, and multi-sensor surveys, generated different datasets (Table II). Among these, TLS surveys exhibited the highest point density.

TABLE II. MAIN PARAMETERS OF DATASET USED IN THIS WORK

Device		Dataset parameters		
		Total area (m ²)	Total point	Mean density (p/m ²)
TLS		37,818.1	38,073,840	1,006.76
UAV-based	LiDAR 90°	55,771.4	1,318,242	23.64
	LiDAR 45°	55,771.4	1,284,590	23.03
	LiDAR 45°+90°	55,771.4	2,602,832	46.67
	RGB sensor 90°	55,771.4	6,610,201	118.52
	RGB sensor 90°+45°	55,771.4	8,093,026	145.11

However, despite significant efforts to maximize TLS survey coverage, this PC covered only 68% of the area surveyed by UAVs due to the complex topography of *biancane* landforms.

UAV-based sensors generate PCs of variable quality. The point density improves only when point clouds captured by the same sensor at different angles, are merged.

Roughness analysis (Fig. 2) shows that points' scattering is directly related to higher point density. In the TLS PC, the highest roughness value seems to be directly related to the vegetation cover on top of the *biancane* landforms, and it is lower on the domes' slopes.

Figure 2. Cloud roughness distribution on the analyzed PCs.

On the contrary, roughness is generally lower on the UAV-based PCs, due to the lower number of points generated. In this case, the highest values span the whole PC, not only vegetation. UAV-based RGB PCs show a lower roughness than LiDAR PCs, according to the smoothest surface derived from the photogrammetry processing. By merging different UAV-based points clouds, also the roughness increases, confirming that this parameter is influenced by a greater number of points.

Even if the TLS PC has the highest roughness, this parameter decreases more rapidly than what is observed on the UAV-based PCs.

Differences in the dataset used are also highlighted by comparing the high density (Table II) merged (i.e. 45°+90°) UAV-based RGB PC, with the TLS PC. Multiple, horizontal, cross sections through these combined PCs (Fig. 3), disclose the points setting on each dataset. Such configuration indicates a more accurate slope reproduction on TLS PC than on UAV-based RGB PC. The cloud of difference (CoD) obtained from the M3C2 plugin (Fig. 4) shows better surface records specifics using the terrestrial device, which reproduces slopes features. Both herbaceous vegetation on micropediments, and other features at the slope foot, seem to cause points scattering on the model. The CoD also highlights that the TLS survey is not continuous with respect to UAV-based monitoring.

Figure 3. I Multiple cross sections obtained through TLS (green, yellow, red scale), and UAV-based (45°+90°) RGB (gray scale) PCs of a slope of one single dome landform.

Figure 4. I Multiscale Model to Model Cloud Comparison (M3C2) between UAV-based (45°+90°) RGB and Terrestrial Laser Scanner PCs. Color scale on the right indicates distance between PCs

However, TLS high-quality-survey is confirmed by comparing in-situ, and 3D model rill width measurements, performed on marked features clearly recognizable on the TLS PC (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Measurements of the rill width carried out with the TLS PC at marked features compared to corresponding in-situ measurements

IV. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

This preliminary study confirms that high-resolution PCs, obtained from TLS and UAV-based surveys, have different

characteristics when used in a complex terrain morphology. Point density is significantly higher for TLS PC than for UAV-based surveys. TLS survey produces high-detailed PC that quite accurately reproduces slopes surface complexity. Based on *in situ* monitoring, TLS data seem to offer a superior resolution than UAV-based PCs, and measurements on TLS PC are similar to those collected in field surveys. In fact, the roughness is proportionally lower, and the points are less scattered on the scene, better reproducing the details occurring on the domes' slopes.

However, on complex landscapes, such those we have been monitoring, TLS technology is a time-consuming survey requiring many scan positions, in order to acquire the landforms' features since both domes' morphology, and vegetation, obstacle the laser flight. TLS implementation requires long time (order of hours) of dedicated processing, and PCs are affected by great uncertainties such as registration, and georeferencing errors.

On the contrary, UAV-based surveys can provide broader, and full scene coverage, a lower impact of registration, and less georeferencing errors, therefore representing an easy and quick procedure.

UAV-based sensors affect PCs densities. In fact, UAV-based RGB processing produces denser PC than UAV-based LiDAR. By merging PCs acquired from the same sensor at different angles, we improved the datasets, as the number of points increases per square meter. Even though the TLS PCs are characterized by a greater point density than the UAV-based PCs, and the quality, the density, and the accuracy of TLS PC are higher than those of UAV-based PCs, an integrated survey can help in the full coverage of the articulated *biancane* morphology. In fact, by merging high-detailed TLS PCs of dome slopes in the UAV-based PC, we can obtain full coverage of the landscape maintaining the main information about geomorphological process acting on slopes.

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